

Direct C–H Arylation of Dithiophene-Tetrathiafulvalene: Tuneable Electronic Properties and 2D Self-Assembled Molecular Networks at the Solid/Liquid Interface**

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Abstract: Tetrathiafulvalene is among the best known building blocks in molecular electronics due to its outstanding electron-donating and redox properties. Among its derivatives, dithiophene-tetrathiafulvalene (DT-TTF) has attracted considerable interest in organic electronics, owing to its high field-effect mobility. Herein, we report the direct C–H arylation of DT-TTF to synthesise mono- and tetraarylated derivatives functionalised with electron-withdrawing and electron-donating groups in order to evaluate their influence on the electronic properties by cyclic voltammetry, UV-vis spectroscopy and theoretical calculations. Self-assembly of

the DT-TTF-tetrabenzoic acid derivative was studied by using scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) which revealed the formation of ordered, densely packed 2D hydrogen-bonded networks at the graphite/liquid interface. The tetrabenzoic acid derivative can attain a planar geometry on the graphite surface due to van der Waals interactions with the surface and H-bonding with neighbouring molecules. This study demonstrates a simple method for the synthesis of arylated DT-TTF derivatives towards the design and construction of novel π -extended electroactive frameworks.

Introduction

Tetrathiafulvalene (TTF) and its numerous derivatives are among the most versatile electroactive organic molecules due to their remarkable redox properties, their use as building blocks for the development of molecular conductors, and diverse applications in organic electronics.^[1,2] TTF derivatives

have also been widely explored as molecular switches, sensors, rectifiers, transistors, and for nonlinear optics, among other uses.^[3–7] More recently and since the pioneering study reporting the palladium-catalysed direct C–H arylation,^[8] tetraarylated TTFs have been employed for the construction of functional porous frameworks^[9] such as metal–organic frameworks (MOFs),^[10–12] covalent organic frameworks (COFs)^[13,14] as well as hydrogen-bonded organic frameworks (HOFs).^[15,16] However, direct C–H arylation has been limited to TTF derivatives,^[8,17] having a great interest in the catalytic peripheral modification of other π -extended TTF cores for the construction of electroactive frameworks exhibiting new electronic properties and functions.

Among TTF derivatives, dithiophene-tetrathiafulvalene (DT-TTF; Scheme 1) received considerable attention as an active material for organic field-effect transistors (OFETs) due to its high OFET mobility.^[18–20] In contrast to neutral TTF which exhibits a twisted boat-like conformation, the DT-TTF molecule is completely planar in the solid state, and its oxidation potential ($E^{\circ}_{1ox} = 0.78$ V, $E^{\circ}_{2ox} = 0.96$ V vs SCE) is higher than that of TTF leading to improved ambient stability.^[1,21] To optimise the OFET performance, one strategy involves adjusting the electronic structure of the electroactive molecules to align their

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Scheme 1. Molecular structures of TTF and DT-TTF.

HOMO energy level with the work function of the electrode (e.g., 5.1 eV for gold).^[20] In this sense, the incorporation of electron-withdrawing or electron-donating groups is an efficient strategy to fine-tune the HOMO and/or LUMO energy levels.^[8,22] However, so far, no studies on the direct functionalisation of DT-TTF building blocks allowing the modulation of its electronic properties have been reported.

Given the importance of TTF- and DT-TTF based systems in organic electronics, the study of their organisation in thin films such as H-bond based self-assembled molecular networks (SAMNs) adsorbed on solid substrates is desired. The use of scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) allows the direct visualisation of SAMNs, enabling the study of their domain size, presence of defects as well as intermolecular bonding landscape. In particular, the self-assembly of TTF derivatives on conductive substrates such as highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) has been studied previously.^[23–29]

Herein, we report the synthesis and characterization of a family of arylated DT-TTF derivatives 2–5 (Scheme 2) obtained via palladium-catalysed direct C–H arylation. Monoarylated DT-TTF derivatives functionalised with $-\text{NO}_2$ (2) or $-\text{NMe}_2$ (3) substituents were synthesised to evaluate their influence on the HOMO and LUMO energy levels. In addition, tetraarylated DT-TTFs bearing ester (4) or acid (5) groups were prepared, both of which displayed a nonplanar configuration as revealed by density functional theory (DFT) calculations. STM studies revealed that the DT-TTF-tetrabenzoic acid derivative 5 forms densely packed 2D self-assembled networks at the heptanoic acid/graphite interface. Furthermore, molecular models based on experimentally measured unit cell parameters suggest that 5 lies flat on the graphite surface due to van der Waals interactions with the surface as well as H-bonding with neighbouring 5 building blocks.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis of DT-TTF and arylated DT-TTF derivatives

DT-TTF was synthesised according to described procedures.^[30] This six-step synthetic route provides a higher yield than those previously reported (Scheme S1 in the Supporting

Scheme 2. Molecular structures of the arylated DT-TTF derivatives (2–5) synthesised in this study.

Information).^[31] Arylated DT-TTF derivatives were obtained by optimising a reported synthetic procedure based on the palladium-catalysed direct C–H arylation of aromatic compounds with aryl halides.^[8,32] In this study, we selected aryl bromides functionalised with electron-withdrawing $-\text{NO}_2$ (2) or electron-donating $-\text{NMe}_2$ (3) substituents to evaluate their influence on the electronic properties of DT-TTF. We focused only on monoarylated derivatives for comparative purposes.^[8] Reaction of DT-TTF (1; 1 equiv.) with aryl bromides (1 equiv.) in the presence of caesium carbonate, tri-*tert*-butylphosphonium tetrafluoroborate and palladium acetate (5 mol%) in THF under reflux yielded the monoarylated derivatives 2 and 3 in 13% and 48% yields, respectively (Scheme 3). The lower yield in the case of using electron-withdrawing aryl bromides such as Br---Ar---NO_2 has also been observed in other direct C–H arylation reactions under similar conditions.^[33] The modest yields in the monoarylation reactions can be explained by the formation of di- and triarylated derivatives, which were identified in both reactions.

In order to study the formation of 2D self-assembled molecular networks at the solid/liquid interface, the synthesis of carboxylic acids is desirable to promote the formation of hydrogen-bonding intermolecular interactions.^[34,35] The synthesis of the non-methylated benzoic acid derivative was initially explored, but its isolation was not achieved because of its poor solubility and difficult purification. Solubility was improved by introducing a methyl group onto the phenyl moieties, which also influenced the planarity of the molecule (see DFT calculations below). Tetraarylated DT-TTF derivative 4 was obtained in good yield (85%) using an excess (5 equiv.) of ethyl 4-bromo-3-methylbenzoate and a larger amount of palladium acetate (5 mol%; Scheme 4). Saponification of 4 with NaOH under reflux yielded the DT-TTF tetrabenzoic acid derivative 5 which was fully characterised by multiple spectroscopic techniques. Although a needle-shaped microcrystalline material was observed as revealed by PXRD and SEM microscopy (Figures S23 and S24), it was not possible to obtain high-quality single crystals to solve the crystal structure of 5.

Electrochemical and optical properties

The electrochemical properties of DT-TTF derivatives 1–4 were investigated by cyclic voltammetry (CV) using $n\text{Bu}_4\text{NPF}_6$ (0.15 M) as electrolyte in CH_2Cl_2 at room temperature (Figure 1). Cyclic voltammogram of unsubstituted DT-TTF (1) shows two redox processes assigned to the oxidation to the radical cation DT-

Scheme 3. Pd-catalysed C–H monoarylation of DT-TTF with electron-withdrawing ($-\text{NO}_2$; 2) and -donating ($-\text{NMe}_2$; 3) functional groups.

Scheme 4. Pd-catalysed C–H tetraarylation of DT-TTF functionalised with –COOEt (**4**) and –COOH (**5**) groups.

Figure 1. Cyclic voltammograms of **1** (DT-TTF), monoaryl (**2**, **3**) and tetraaryl (**4**) DT-TTF derivatives in CH_2Cl_2 vs. Fc/Fc^+ using $n\text{Bu}_4\text{NPF}_6$ (0.15 M) as electrolyte at 0.3 V/s scan rate.

TTF^+ ($E_{\text{ox1}} = +0.29$ V vs Fc/Fc^+) and dication DT-TTF^{2+} ($E_{\text{ox2}} = +0.74$ V vs Fc/Fc^+) species. The first ($E_{\text{ox1}} = +0.38$ V vs Fc/Fc^+) and second ($E_{\text{ox2}} = +0.83$ V vs Fc/Fc^+) oxidation potentials increase in **2** in comparison to the unsubstituted DT-TTF **1** due to the incorporation of the electron-withdrawing $-\text{NO}_2$ substituent. In contrast, oxidation potentials of **3** ($E_{\text{ox1}} = +0.27$ V; $E_{\text{ox2}} = +0.73$ V vs Fc/Fc^+) slightly decrease when introducing electron-

donating groups, indicating an almost negligible impact on the HOMO energy level (Table 1). Oxidation potentials of **4** also show positive shifts relative to those of **1** which is consistent with the presence of four ester groups. CV of **5** using $n\text{Bu}_4\text{NPF}_6$ (0.15 M) as electrolyte in DMSO (Figure S25) shows a reversible redox peak attributed to the oxidation to the radical cation DT-TTF^+ and an irreversible redox process at higher potentials, which could be related to the irreversible decarboxylation process upon oxidation initiated by the Kolbe reaction.^[10,36,37] The HOMO energy levels of **1–5** were estimated from the onset of the first oxidation redox process (Table 1) using the following equation: $E_{\text{HOMO}} = -e(4.8 + E_{1/2})$.

Figure 2 shows the UV-vis spectra of DT-TTF derivatives **1–5** measured in CHCl_3 or DMSO (0.05 mM) at room temperature. While absorption spectra of **1** and **3** remain similar, the absorption bands of **2**, **4** and **5** are red-shifted due to the electron-withdrawing character of the substituents. The optical gaps (E_g) for **1–5** were calculated from the onset of the most red-shifted band in the UV-vis spectra and were, in turn, used to estimate the energy of the LUMOs ($E_{\text{LUMO}} = E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_g$; Table 1).

DFT calculations

All compounds were systematically explored using DFT models at the B3LYP-6-31G(d,p) level, revealing that the DT-TTF moiety

Table 1. Summary of HOMO–LUMO energy levels estimated experimentally and computed theoretically for **1–5**. **1*** corresponds to the flat D_{2h} conformation, which is not a minimum (see text).

	CV + UV-vis			DFT calculations		
	E_{HOMO} [eV]	E_{LUMO} [eV]	E_g [eV]	E_{HOMO} [eV]	E_{LUMO} [eV]	E_g [eV]
1	–5.01	–1.62	3.39	–5.34	–1.37	3.03
1*				–5.14	–1.50	2.69
2	–5.11	–2.80	2.31	–5.41	–3.04	1.99
3	–4.99	–1.60	3.39	–5.12	–1.36	2.99
4	–5.12	–2.43	2.69	–5.33	–2.10	2.77
5	–5.06	–2.47	2.59	–5.33	–2.24	2.63

Figure 2. UV-vis spectra of 0.05 mM solutions of **1** (DT-TTF), **2**, **3**, and **4** in CH_2Cl_2 , and **5** in DMSO.

adopts a boat conformation with a low stabilisation energy with respect to its planar counterparts of circa 1 kcal/mol for 1 and 2 kcal/mol for 2 and 3. This low energy matches the fact that 1 is flat in the solid state^[18,38] whereas in vacuum and in CH₂Cl₂ continuum the presence of imaginary frequencies indicates that this is not a minimum (Figure 3). For 4 and 5, the more extensive functionalization implies a larger energetic penalty, 18 kcal/mol, when compared to planar conformations. This is due to the increased number of functional groups and larger steric hindrance from the extra methyl groups. The HOMO and LUMO energy levels and optical gaps were computed at the B3LYP-6-311+G(2d,p)-CH₂Cl₂/B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)-CH₂Cl₂ level and give trends in reasonable agreement with experimental observations (Table 1 and Figure S26). DFT results for both conformations of 1 show that the effect of the conformation on the electronic properties is far from negligible. In addition, 2, 4, and 5 show a strongly reduced density on the TTF DT-TTF moiety (Figure 3) which accounts for the large stabilisation estimated experimentally. The HOMOs densities are more homogenous in 1, 2, 4, and 5 showing very similar densities localised on the DT-TTF moiety, and only 3 shows a different density.

As shown in Table 1, both the HOMO and LUMO energy levels are lowered in the monoarylated nitro derivative 2, resulting in a significant decrease in the HOMO–LUMO gap (from 3.39 to 2.31 eV). In contrast, the introduction of the electron-donating –NMe₂ group into the DT-TTF core in 3 has an almost negligible effect on the HOMO and LUMO energy levels. Although the corresponding tetraarylated derivatives were not synthesised, DFT calculations suggest that the influence on the HOMO and LUMO energy levels is more pronounced with increasing number of substituents (Figure S27).

STM studies

Compound 5 was selected for characterization using STM due to the presence of carboxylic groups on the DT-TTF backbone which are known to facilitate the formation of hydrogen-bonded self-assembled networks. The self-assembly of 5 at the heptanoic acid/graphite interface was studied using STM. 5 forms long-range ordered crystalline networks at the heptanoic acid/graphite interface with domains extending over 150 nm x 150 nm. Large scale STM images show bright features ordered in a pseudo hexagonal arrangement (Figures 4a, b and S28). Smaller-scale STM image presented in Figure 4b shows a well-ordered arrangement of bright features which can be assigned to the electron-rich DT-TTF core of 5. Unit cell parameters extracted from graphite calibrated STM images are $a=1.9\pm 0.1$ nm, $b=2.3\pm 0.1$ nm, $\gamma=62\pm 1^\circ$, which suggests the existence of a distorted hexagonal network. A molecular model built using calibrated STM data is shown in Figure 4c. The molecular model reveals that 5 forms one-dimensional hydrogen-bonded chains using two diagonally opposite carboxyl groups present on the DT-TTF backbone. The remaining two carboxyl groups are thus not engaged in hydrogen bonding with neighbouring DT-TTF molecules and most likely interact with partially adsorbed molecules of heptanoic acid which was used as the solvent. The molecular model also reveals substantial empty areas between the hydrogen-bonded 1D arrays of 5. These areas are possibly filled with partially/transiently adsorbed heptanoic acid molecules which are mobile on the time scale of STM measurements. The observation of partial hydrogen bonding between the molecules of 5 is not completely surprising. It is well known that molecular materials, especially those forming porous networks do not always scale with the size of the building blocks. This is because increased pore sizes are thermodynamically disfavoured and go against the natural tendency of close packing. If the molecules of 5 were to form a 2D network based on hydrogen bonding

Figure 3. Molecular structures computed at the B3LYP-631G(d,p)-CH₂Cl₂ level, from the side and top with corresponding HOMOs and LUMOs.

Figure 4. a) Large-scale and b) high-resolution STM images. c) Molecular model of a self-assembled molecular network of **5** adsorbed at the heptanoic acid/HOPG interface. Unit cell parameters: $a = 1.9 \pm 0.1$ nm, $b = 2.3 \pm 0.1$ nm, angle = $62^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. Imaging parameters: $I_{\text{set}} = 100$ pA, $U_{\text{bias}} = -1.2$ V.

using its all four carboxyl groups, the resultant cavities would be too big to be stable under ambient conditions at the solution-solid interface. Thus, the system must make a compromise between forming strong twofold hydrogen bonds between the remaining carboxyl groups and close packing. Under the experimental conditions used, the latter seems to be the choice. Such scalability study has been previously reported for self-assembled networks of aromatic tricarboxylic acids.^[39]

Considering that intermolecular H-bonds formed between carboxylic acid groups are highly directional, it is likely that **5** reaches a planar geometry to form such SAMNs, as supported by the molecular model shown in Figure 4c and further calculations shown in Figure 5. This planarization is the result of van der Waals interactions between the HOPG surface and the DT-TTF core extended with phenyl groups.

Conclusion

In summary, we have reported a simple synthetic procedure based on Pd-catalysed direct C–H arylation to obtain a new family of mono- and tetraarylated DT-TTF derivatives bearing different functional groups (**2**–**5**). The HOMO and LUMO energy levels of DT-TTF were modulated by introducing an electron-withdrawing $-\text{NO}_2$ substituent onto the aryl group (**2**), whereas the electron-donating dimethylamino group in **3** has an almost

Figure 5. Optimised molecular structure of **5** on a graphene flake at the GNF2-xTB level (3 views).

negligible impact on the electronic properties of DT-TTF. In addition, long-range ordered crystalline hydrogen-bonded networks of DT-TTF tetrabenzoic acid derivative **5** were observed at the graphite/liquid interface as revealed by STM studies. Interestingly, molecule **5** can reach a planar geometry on the graphite surface due to van der Waals interactions with the surface as well as H-bonding with neighbouring molecules, as supported by molecular models based on experimentally measured unit-cell parameters. This study opens the way to exploring the design of new extended electroactive frameworks such as MOFs or COFs based on DT-TTF building blocks, which are of great interest due to their promising electronic properties.

Experimental Section

General procedure for the synthesis of 1: DT-TTF (**1**) molecule was synthesised as previously reported (see the Supporting Information).^[30]

General procedure for the synthesis of 2: Pd(OAc)₂ (1.0 mg, 0.004 mmol), PtBu₃•HBF₄ (3.7 mg, 0.013 mmol), and Cs₂CO₃ (90.3 mg, 0.3 mmol) were placed in a 25 mL reaction flask under inert (N₂) atmosphere. Anhydrous THF (2 mL) was added and the mixture was stirred for 10 min at 55 °C. A solution of DT-TTF (**1**)^[30] (27.0 mg, 0.085 mmol) and 1-bromo-4-nitrobenzene (17.2 mg, 0.085 mmol) in anhydrous THF (2.0 mL) was added to the flask and the mixture was heated at 85 °C for 3 h under inert atmosphere. The organic residue was extracted with CHCl₃, washed with water (3 × 5 mL), and dried with anhydrous MgSO₄. Chromatographic purification on silica gel using CHCl₂/hexane (1:1) as eluent afforded **2** as an orange solid (5 mg, 13.4% yield). Characterisation: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 6.93 (s, 2H), 6.99 (s, 1H), 7.68 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 2H) and 8.30 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 118.2, 121.2, 123.3, 124.2, 127.1, 129.1, 137.7, 140.8, 141.1, 151.3. IR (cm⁻¹): 3105 (w), 2848 (m), 1739 (w), 1600 (m), 1514 (m), 1333 (s), 1109 (m), 842 (m), 746 (m) and 693 (m). CV (Bu₄NPF₆ 0.1 M in CH₂Cl₂ as electrolyte; V vs. Fc/Fc⁺): $E_{1/2}^1 = 0.38$ V; $E_{1/2}^2 = 0.83$ V. HR-ESI TOF-MS: Observed (m/z) = 436.88168 ($\Delta = -4.8$ ppm). Calcd for C₁₆H₇NO₂S₆ = 436.87956. UV-Vis (in CHCl₃) λ (nm) (ε [M⁻¹ cm⁻¹]): 317 (168400) and 359 (126000).

General procedure for the synthesis of 3: Pd(OAc)₂ (4 mg, 0.018 mmol), PtBu₃•HBF₄ (14 mg, 0.07 mmol), and Cs₂CO₃ (350 mg, 0.994 mmol) were placed in a 50 mL reaction flask under inert (N₂) atmosphere. Anhydrous THF (7 mL) was added and the mixture was

stirred for 10 min at 55 °C. A solution of DT-TTF (1)^[30] (103.4 mg, 0.327 mmol) and 4-bromo-N,N-dimethylaniline (63.4 mg, 0.317 mmol) in anhydrous THF (8.0 mL) was added to the flask and the mixture was heated at 85 °C for 3 h under inert atmosphere. The organic residue was extracted with CH₂Cl₂, washed with water (3 × 5 mL) and dried with MgSO₄. Chromatographic purification on silica gel by using mixtures of hexane and CH₂Cl₂/hexane (1:1) as eluent afforded **3** (68 mg, 48% yield) as a yellow solid. Characterisation: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 3.01 (s, 6H), 6.75 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.89 (s, 3H) and 7.42 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 40.4, 108.9, 112.1, 112.4, 118.8, 120.7, 127.2, 128.5, 131.3, 135.7 and 149.9. IR (cm⁻¹): 3097 (s), 2919 (s), 2850 (s), 1613 (s), 1539 (s), 1497 (s), 1332 (s), 1225 (m), 1193 (m) and 757 (s). CV (Bu₄NPF₆ 0.1 M in CH₂Cl₂ as electrolyte; V vs. Fc/Fc⁺): *E*_{1/2}¹ = 0.28 V; *E*_{1/2}² = 0.73 V. HR-ESI TOF-MS: Observed (*m/z*) = 434.93879 (Δ = -4.8 ppm). Calcd for C₁₈H₁₃NS₆ = 434.93668. UV-Vis (in CHCl₃) λ (nm) (ε [M⁻¹ cm⁻¹]): 310 (199400) and 412 (9400).

General procedure for the synthesis of 4: Pd(OAc)₂ (20 mg, 0.09 mmol), PtBu₃•HBF₄ (70 mg, 0.24 mmol), and Cs₂CO₃ (500 mg, 1.5 mmol) were placed in a 50 mL reaction flask under inert (N₂) atmosphere. Anhydrous THF (5 mL) was added, and the mixture was stirred for 10 min at 55 °C. A solution of DT-TTF (1)^[30] (50 mg, 0.23 mmol) and ethyl 4-bromo-3-methylbenzoate (365 mg, 1.5 mmol) in anhydrous THF (5.0 mL) was added to the flask and the mixture was heated at 75 °C for 15 h under inert (N₂) atmosphere. The organic residue was extracted with CHCl₃, washed with water (3 × 5 mL), and dried with anhydrous MgSO₄. Chromatographic purification on silica gel by using CHCl₃ as an eluent afforded **4** (130 mg, 85% yield) as an orange solid. Characterisation: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 1.40 (t, *J* = 3.5 Hz, 12H), 2.37 (s, 12H), 4.39 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 8H), 7.47 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 4H), 7.90 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 4H) and 7.95 (s, 4H). ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 14.3, 20.7, 61.2, 119.1, 127.2, 128.2, 130.2, 130.9, 131.9, 133.9, 136.1, 166.2. IR (cm⁻¹): 1717 (s, C=O), 1605 (m), 1479 (m), 1293 (s), 1266 (s), 1246 (s), 1190 (s), 1143 (s), 1127 (s), 1104 (s), 1026 (s) and 756 (s). CV (Bu₄NPF₆ 0.1 M in CH₂Cl₂ as electrolyte; V vs. Fc/Fc⁺): *E*_{1/2}¹ = 0.39 V; *E*_{1/2}² = 0.79 V. HR-ESI TOF-MS: Observed (*m/z*) = 964.13544 (Δ = 0.67 ppm). Calcd for C₅₀H₄₄O₈S₆ = 964.13550. UV-Vis (in CHCl₃) λ (nm) (ε [M⁻¹ cm⁻¹]): 308 (134400) and 337 (55800).

General procedure for the synthesis of 5: A 50 mL flask was charged with **4** (100 mg, 0.10 mmol) and subjected to three cycles of vacuum/N₂. Degassed MeOH (4 mL) and anhydrous THF (4 mL) were added to generate a suspension. In a separate flask, NaOH (50 mg, 1.1 mmol) was dissolved in degassed water (4 mL). The sodium hydroxide solution was added to **4** under inert atmosphere and the reaction was heated to reflux for 12 h. The reaction was then cooled to room temperature and the THF was removed under vacuum. A 1 M solution of HCl (5 mL) was added to afford an orange precipitate, which was collected by filtration and washed with water (20 mL) and CH₂Cl₂ (20 mL). The product was collected and dried under vacuum for 12 h to afford **5** as a light orange solid (70 mg, 94% yield). Characterisation: ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ (ppm) = 2.44 (s, 12H), 7.55 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 4H), 7.85 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 4H), 7.93 (s, 4H) and 13.10 (s, 4H). IR (cm⁻¹): 2927 (m, O-H), 1723 (s, C=O), 1693 (m), 1605 (m), 1297 (m), 1266 (m), 1193 (m) and 758 (s). HR-ESI TOF-MS: Observed (*m/z*) = 851.00717 (Δ = 1.36 ppm). Calcd for C₄₂H₂₇O₈S₆ = 851.00357.

Materials and methods: All reagents and solvents were of high purity grade and were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co., and TCI. ¹H liquid NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE 300 spectrometer (300 MHz). Chemical shifts (δ) are quoted in ppm and the coupling constants (*J*) in Hz. Chemical shifts were reported in ppm relative to an internal standard CDCl₃ (δ = 7.26 ppm for ¹H, 77.16 ppm for ¹³C) or DMSO-*d*₆ (δ = 2.50 ppm for ¹H). Tetramethylsilane was used as the internal reference. Infrared spectra were recorded on an ATR FTIR GALAXY SERIES FTIR 7000 (Mattson Instruments) spectrometer in the

4000–400 cm⁻¹ range using powdered samples. High-resolution Mass Spectrometry: Experiments were performed on a Solaris XR FT-ICR MS (Bruker Daltonics, Billerica, MA), equipped with a 7T actively shielded magnet. Ions were generated using a Combi MALDI-electrospray ionization (ESI) source. Ionization was achieved by electrospray, using a voltage of 4500 V applied to the needle, and a counter voltage of 300 V applied to the capillary. Samples were prepared by adding a spray solution of acetonitrile/water (70:30, v/v) with 0.1% of Formic Acid to a solution of the sample at a v/v ratio of 1 to 5% to give the best signal-to-noise ratio. UV/visible absorption spectra were recorded on a Jasco V-780 spectrometer. TLC analyses were performed on commercial glass plates bearing a 0.25-mm layer of Merck Silica gel 60F254. Preparative separations were performed by silica gel chromatography (Wako gel C-200). The electrochemical experiments were performed on an Autolab electrochemical workstation (PGSTAT302 N with FRA32 M Module) connected to a personal computer that uses Nova 2.1 electrochemical software. A typical three-electrode experimental cell equipped with a glassy carbon as the working electrode, platinum wire as the counter electrode, and silver wire as the pseudoreference electrode was used for the electrochemical characterization. The electrochemical properties were studied by measuring CV under an inert (N₂) atmosphere at different scan rates in previously N₂-purged 0.1 M *n*Bu₄NPF₆/CH₂Cl₂ solutions. Ferrocene (Fc) was added as an internal standard upon completion of each experiment. All potentials are reported in V versus Fc/Fc⁺.

DFT calculations: DFT calculations were performed with Gaussian 09.^[40] For this, different molecular structures with different symmetry groups were generated and minimised at the B3LYP-6-31G(d,p) and the B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)-CH₂Cl₂ levels. All minima were checked for the presence of imaginary frequencies. In addition, selected structures were also reoptimised at the M06-2X-6-31G(d,p)-CH₂Cl₂ giving similar results. The electronic structure, HOMO and LUMO levels, and TD-DFT calculations were performed at the B3LYP-6-311 + G(2d,p)-CH₂Cl₂ level. Vertical ionization potentials and electron affinity calculations were also performed yielding very similar values to the HOMO and LUMO energies reported.

STM studies: Scanning tunnelling microscopy experiments were carried out employing a PicoLE (Keysight) or Molecular Imaging (Agilent Technologies) STM operating in constant-current mode at room temperature. STM tips were mechanically cut by using Pt/Ir wire (80/20, diameter 0.25 mm, Advent Research Materials). Prior to every STM experiment at the solid/liquid interface, highly oriented pyrolytic graphite substrate (grade ZYB, Momentive Performance Materials) was rinsed with acetone and freshly cleaved using Scotch tape. After this, the solution was drop casted on the substrate and the STM imaging was carried out at room temperature. The STM images were obtained within a time range of 3–8 h. 1 mg of solid was weighed and added to 1 mL solvent, that is, as-received heptanoic acid (Merck). Sonication was used to dissolve the materials which resulted in a saturated solution. After this, a 10% dilution was created in the same solvent. STM imaging parameters such as *I*_{set} and *U*_{bias} are shown in each figure and correspond to the tunnelling current and applied substrate bias. STM images were graphite-calibrated using scanning probe imaging processor software (SPIP, Image Metrology). Molecular models were created using HyperChem™ software (version 8.0.1) as described in the Supporting Information.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: cyclic voltammetry · DFT calculations · dithiophene-tetrathiafulvalene · self-assembled molecular networks · scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM)

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